

PLENARY PAPER

**HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES - MATRIX PROPERTY/
COMPOSITE PROPERTY RELATIONSHIPS**

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ABSTRACT

The relationship between the property of a composite material and the property of its constituent matrix will be discussed. Results will be presented for the fracture, impact, fatigue and creep properties of various advanced carbon fibre reinforced composites. These results will be related to the modulus, strength and fracture toughness of the resins used.